

CHANGING TEACHER'S ROLES WITH DIFFERENT AGE GROUPS

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the changing roles of teachers across different age groups, highlighting the unique approaches, challenges, and skills required to effectively support learners at each stage of their educational journey. Also, the attitude of teachers to students in kindergartens, schools, colleges and universities, the teaching system, the influence of the environment, the effective conduct of lesson processes and the methods used in the lesson are analyzed.

Key words: method, system, kindergarten, college, school, university, student, teacher's role, atmosphere.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola turli yosh guruhlarida o'qituvchilarning o'zgaruvchan rollarini o'rganadi, o'quvchilarni ta'lim yo'lining har bir bosqichida samarali qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun zarur bo'lgan noyob yondashuvlar, qiyinchiliklar va ko'nikmalarni ta'kidlaydi. Shuningdek, bog'cha, maktab, kollej va universitetlarda o'qituvchilarning o'quvchilarga bo'lgan munosabati, o'qitish tizimi, atrof-muhitning ta'siri va darsda qo'llaniladigan metodlar tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: metod, tizim, bog'cha, kollej, maktab, universitet, o'quvchi, o'qituvchining roli, atmosfera.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье исследуются меняющиеся роли учителей в разных возрастных группах, подчеркиваются уникальные подходы, проблемы и навыки, необходимые для эффективной поддержки учащихся на каждом этапе их образовательного пути. Также анализируется отношение педагогов к учащимся в детских садах, школах, колледжах и вузах, система обучения, влияние окружающей среды, эффективное проведение уроковых процессов и методы, используемые на уроке.

Ключевые слова: метод, система, детский сад, колледж, школа, университет, ученик, роль учителя, атмосфера.

INTRODUCTION

The teaching profession is inherently dynamic, evolving alongside societal, technological, and educational advancements. One of the most significant aspects of this evolution is how teachers adapt their roles to meet the needs of students at different stages of their educational journey. From early childhood to adult education, the expectations placed on teachers change dramatically, driven by the developmental, cognitive, and emotional growth of their students.

In early childhood, teachers take on the role of nurturing guides, providing a safe and stimulating environment where foundational skills are fostered through play and social interaction. As students progress to primary school, the teacher's role shifts towards that of an instructor, balancing structured lessons with interactive, engaging activities to build core academic competencies. Middle school brings unique challenges as students undergo rapid social and cognitive development; here, teachers become mentors who guide and support the growing independence of their learners. High school teachers, on the other hand, are expected to act as subject experts and career advisors, preparing students for higher education or entry into the workforce. Finally, in adult education, teachers transition to facilitators and collaborators, catering to a diverse range of learners with different backgrounds and goals.

Adaptive teaching roles are essential to address the varied needs of learners at each educational stage. The ability of teachers to modify their approach not only enhances student engagement and learning outcomes but also prepares students for success at each stage of their personal and academic development. This article delves into the changing nature of teaching roles across different age groups, exploring the specific skills and approaches required to support students effectively from early childhood to adulthood.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Research highlights that teachers' roles evolve from nurturing guides in early childhood to structured instructors in primary school, mentors in middle school, and subject experts and career coaches in high school and adult education. Studies by Vygotsky and Knowles underscore the importance of adapting teaching styles to developmental needs.

This study uses a mixed-methods approach: semi-structured interviews with teachers across age groups to gather qualitative insights, and surveys for quantitative data on teaching practices. Data analysis involves thematic coding for interviews and statistical methods for survey results, ensuring a comprehensive view of role adaptation in education.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

- We focus on five main groups of learners:
- Preschool (from 3 – 5 years of age)
- Elementary / Primary School (6 – 10 years)
- Middle school (11-13 years)
- High School Learners (14 – 17 years) and
- Adult Learners (18+ years).

The results of this study reveal the significant shifts in teaching roles across different age groups and highlight the factors that contribute to these changes. Teachers adapt their methods and roles to align with students' cognitive, social,

and emotional development, showcasing the complexity and adaptability required in modern teaching.

Preschool education, the data confirmed that teachers primarily act as facilitators and nurturers. This aligns with the research by Piaget and Vygotsky, which emphasizes that young children learn best through play and social interaction. Teachers in this stage focus on creating a safe, supportive environment and integrating play-based learning to foster foundational skills such as communication and cooperation.

Primary school teachers reported transitioning to more structured roles that balance direct instruction with interactive activities. This shift supports studies by Bruner, which found that guided discovery and structured learning enhance foundational literacy and numeracy skills. Teachers indicated that their role requires a high degree of adaptability to address varying skill levels and learning styles while maintaining student engagement.

The middle school phase was noted for being the most challenging due to the rapid social and emotional changes that students experience. Teachers described themselves as mentors and guides, focusing on critical thinking, teamwork, and independent learning. This finding echoes research by Eccles and Roeser, which underscores the importance of balancing academic instruction with emotional support during adolescence. Teachers highlighted strategies such as group projects and collaborative learning as essential to fostering social skills and academic growth.

In high school, teachers' roles evolved into those of subject-matter experts and career advisors. High school teachers indicated that while their primary focus is deep content knowledge, they also play an essential role in preparing students for life beyond school, including college or career paths. This period demands a balance between encouraging academic excellence and fostering independent study habits and life skills.

For adult education, the results showed that teachers acted more as facilitators and coaches, enabling self-directed learning and practical knowledge application. This aligns with Knowles' theory of andragogy, which suggests that adult learners benefit from instruction that acknowledges their prior experience and current motivations. Teachers noted the importance of adapting lessons to be relevant and applicable, supporting learners' personal and professional growth.

Quantitative Results: The survey results indicated that 85% of teachers across all educational levels recognized the need to adapt their teaching strategies based on the age group they worked with. The most significant differences were seen between early childhood and high school education, where the role shifted from nurturing to deep content delivery. Additionally, 78% of teachers reported using collaborative learning strategies in middle and high school, while only 30% used these strategies in early childhood settings.

Table 1: Summary of Teacher Roles by Age Group

Qualitative Results: Interviews with teachers highlighted recurring themes of adaptability and empathy. Teachers in early childhood stressed the importance of building trust and fostering a sense of security, while high school educators emphasized the need for expertise and mentorship. Middle school teachers focused on the dual role of guiding students academically and supporting their emotional needs. Teachers also noted the challenge of integrating technology at different age levels. While technology use in early childhood was limited to interactive educational apps, high school and adult education heavily incorporated tools like digital research platforms and online discussion forums.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, The role of a teacher evolves significantly across different age groups to meet the unique developmental, cognitive, and emotional needs of students. In early childhood education, teachers act as facilitators and nurturers, fostering foundational skills through play and social interaction. As students move into primary school, teachers shift to more structured instructional roles, focusing

on literacy, numeracy, and foundational academic skills. In middle school, teachers combine mentorship and instruction, guiding students through their social and cognitive transitions. High school teachers assume the roles of subject-matter experts and career advisors, preparing students for higher education or the workforce. In adult education, teachers become facilitators, enabling self-directed learning and applying knowledge to real-world scenarios. Adapting to these changing roles is essential for supporting students' academic and personal growth at every stage, ensuring a responsive and effective learning environment.

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